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COMET Phase- α Experiment to Investigate COMET's New Muon Beamline at J-PARC

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Abstract

The COMET Phase-I and Phase-II experiments will search for muon-to-electron conversion, a process that violates the charged lepton flavour conservation, with the goal of significantly improving upon the current upper limit for the branching ratio. It involves the construction of dedicated facilities and a beamline at J-PARC, Japan, necessitating comprehensive assessments.

The Phase- α experiment took place in February and March 2023, representing a crucial milestone in commissioning the primary proton beam and investigating the secondary muon beam. For the purposes, we developed simple and effective detectors, including TiO₂ sensors for proton beam monitoring, a plastic scintillating fibre hodoscope, and an assembly to count negative muons. Additionally, a tracking detector originally designed for Phase-I and -II was employed.

The commissioning of the proton beam within the COMET facility was a significant achievement, accompanied by precise measurements of its beam size. Furthermore, the successful transport of the muon beam through the COMET Muon Transport Solenoid, a pivotal beamline component, was confirmed. Notably, the momentum spectrum and beam profile of the transported negative muons are generically aligned with estimations derived from our simulation software.

This article provides a comprehensive overview of Phase- α , encompassing its detectors, preliminary results, and future prospects.

1 Introduction

The COMET experiment will search for muon-to-electron conversion, $\mu^- + N \rightarrow e^- + N$, a process that violates charged lepton flavour conservation at J-PARC, Japan [1]. It will be conducted in two phases: Phase-I and -II. Phase-II aims to achieve a sensitivity of $\mathcal{O}(10^{-17})$, exceeding the current upper limit on the branching ratio, set by the SINDRUM-II experiment [2] by a factor of 10,000. The experiment commences with a high intense proton beam, which is accelerated to 8 GeV within the J-PARC Main Ring synchrotron accelerator and subsequently slow-extracted into the Hadron Beam Facility, as represented in Figure 1. Figure 2 outlines the timing structure of the proton beam and the resultant detector hits. The beam is configured into pulses at intervals of $1.2 \mu\text{sec}$ so that the timing window for detecting signal electrons remains clear of prompt beam backgrounds.

Figure 1: J-PARC in Japan

Figure 2: Timing structure

Dedicated facilities and a specialised muon transport beamline are being finalised to support these objectives. In line with these efforts, the first COMET commissioning run, Phase- α , was performed in February and March 2023. Phase- α serves multiple purposes, including the investigation of the secondary muon beam and the validation of simulations with observed data. It also provided an opportunity to study the primary proton beam's extraction into the COMET facility for the first time.

The layout of Phase- α , as illustrated in Figure 3, features a Pion Production Section and specifically tailored detectors, characterised by simplicity compared to Phase-I and Phase-II. However, the Transport Solenoid (TS) stands out as an exception due to its pivotal role in selectively transporting negative muons to the experimental area. Therefore, the TS represents a focal point of study during Phase- α .

This paper proceeds to describe the experimental setup in Section 2 and preliminary results in Section 3, followed by the conclusion in Section 4.

Figure 3: Phase- α beamline

2 Experimental Setup

The slow-extracted pulsed proton beam is injected into the beam area and focused on the pion production target made of a 1.1 mm-thick carbon composite. An L-shaped stainless steel target is also accommodated within the target chamber, as evident in Figure 4. This serves to measure the proton beam's size by repositioning the beam around it and scanning the secondary particles with a series of plastic scintillating counters placed next to the chamber. Additionally, we have developed TiO_2 sensors [3], as depicted in Figure 5, designed for the monitoring of the scattered portion of the proton beam and installed along our primary beamline.

Figure 4: Pion production target chamber

Figure 5: TiO_2 sensors

The pions generated from the production target disperse, and only a limited portion of them can be directed into the TS. This limitation arises because Phase- α lacks a magnetic field to effectively collect the pions, which exists in Phase-I and -II. The pions decay into muons while being transported, which enter the experimental area. Phase-I and -II need to stop as many of these muons as possible in a muon-stopping target for the search for muon-to-electron conversion. The TS is designed to transport negative-charged particles at around 45 MeV/c, explicitly targeting those muons. It is established that in curved solenoidal magnetic fields, the centre of a charged particle's helical trajectory undergoes vertical drift. The direction and magnitude of this drift are contingent upon the electric charge polarity and momentum of the particle. The low-momentum negative muons can traverse the experimental area due to the presence of dipole magnets aligned with the solenoid to counteract the drift. In contrast, other particles are effectively blocked by the wall.

Figure 6: Schematics and picture of the Phase- α detectors

Figure 6 displays our detectors in the experimental area to measure the incoming muons. The Muon Beam Monitor (MBM) is installed immediately after the TS exit to profile the two-dimensional beam flux. Straw Tube Tracker provides measurements of track parameters for the beam particles with the MBM. The Range Counter (RC) plays a crucial role in counting negative muons to reconstruct the muon flux as a function of momentum and position.

The MBM is a hodoscope consisting of plastic scintillating fibres with a cross-section of $1 \times 1 \text{ mm}^2$ [4]. Figure 7 shows pictures of its external and internal structure with its electronics and a measured profile of the beam particles which hit the RC simultaneously. The fibres are aligned with 128 on each axis, equally spaced to form a plane of $30 \times 30 \text{ cm}^2$. Every fibre is

Figure 7: Muom Beam Monitor

Figure 8: Straw Tube Tracker

connected to a SiPM for readout, and all the SiPMs are held by 3D-printed containers. The newly developed electronics manage the bias voltage for the SiPMs and facilitate the measurement of hit timing with a sufficient time resolution of 3.3 nsec and hit rate tolerance and capacity.

The Straw Tube Tracker is a composite system consisting of drift chambers referred to as straw tubes, each possessing a diameter of 1 cm [5]. Figure 8 provides an overview of its external gas manifolds, straw tubes, and the associated readout electronics. 480 straw tubes are arranged in a dense two-dimensional configuration across two layers on each axis and filled with a gas mixture containing argon and ethane in a volume ratio 50:50. The readout electronics digitise waveforms with a high sampling rate of $10^9/\text{sec}$ [6]. This detector was originally developed for Phase-I, and Phase- α provided our inaugural opportunity to commission it, along with its full readout chain, in a practical setting.

Figure 9: Schematics and picture of the Range Counter

The RC is an assembly of plastic scintillating plates, graphite momentum degrader plates, and a thin copper absorber plate. Figure 9 shows its picture and illustrates how it works to count negative muons. The Beam-Defining Counter (BDC) and T_0 Counter are 0.5 mm-thick scintillators readout by photomultiplier tubes at both ends. The T_1 and T_2 Counters use scintillators with thicknesses of 1 cm and 0.5 cm, respectively, and are read out at one end. A key feature of the RC is the copper absorber's higher density compared to other materials, significantly shortening the effective lifetime of negative muons that come to rest within it. This allows us to distinguish and count them separately based on the time spectrum of the decay electron signals recorded by the T_1 and T_2 Counters. Operationally, the RC generates trigger signals being distributed to the other detectors when it detects simultaneous hits in both the BDC and T_0 Counter while no hits in the T_1 and T_2 Counters. The degrader plates can control the range of the entry momentum of the stopping negative muons with their total thickness. We developed a remote control system to change the degrader thickness and the vertical position of the RC to reconstruct the momentum spectrum and beam profile of the signal negative muons.

3 Results

Proton beam commissioning was carried out successfully. In Figure 10, the left-side images illustrate the optical response of a phosphor plate placed along the beamline before and after our initial beam tuning. It is evident that the beam has effectively converged at the plate's center. Furthermore, we quantitatively determined the beam size by employing the stainless steel target, as depicted on the right side. Additionally, the TiO_2 proton monitor detected distinct signals, likely stemming from scattered protons, as can be seen on Figure 11.

Figure 10: Beam tuning and measured proton beam size

Figure 11: Signal observed by the TiO_2 proton monitor

Figure 12 displays a reconstructed decay time spectrum, with the horizontal axis representing the hit time interval between the T_0 Counter and the T_1 and T_2 Counters. To analyse this spectrum, we employed a dual exponential curve fitting approach, accounting for background contributions originating from random noise and the proton beam bunches. The red-coloured region corresponds to signal electrons originating from the absorber, enabling us to reconstruct the count of stopping muons. Figure 13 provides the shape of the reconstructed momentum spectrum. While the absolute values are still subject to ongoing investigation, the observed spectrum aligns reasonably well with the estimations derived from our simulation.

We also conducted measurements of the beam profile by adjusting the RC position at si points relative to the beam axis, as depicted in Figure 14. The results were normalised using the reconstructed number of muons at the beamline centre, corresponding to the (0, 0) position on the plot. Notably, the observed beam profile is also consistent with our estimations. The RC configuration in this measurement was to measure muons around 40 MeV/c , which falls within the primary momentum range to be transported by the TS, as previously described. Consequently, our findings confirm that muons within this range are appropriately concentrated at the beamline level, as anticipated.

Figure 12: Decay time spectrum

Figure 13: Momentum spectrum

Figure 14: Muon beam profile

4 Conclusion

We carried out the COMET Phase- α experiment in February and March 2023 to assess the facilities constructed for COMET. The proton beam commissioning was successful, and it was effectively injected into the COMET facility, with phase-space parameters measured. We developed sensors and detectors to facilitate measurements of the proton and secondary muon beams.

We achieved the first observation of the muon beam being transported through the 90°-curved Muon Transport Solenoid of COMET. The characteristics of the reconstructed muon momentum spectrum and beam profile are in broad agreement with our expectations based on simulations.

Looking ahead, ongoing analyses will delve into researching the muon transport optics by incorporating data from all detectors and measuring the backward π/μ production cross-section. Additionally, we plan to validate the COMET simulation software, particularly its hadronic physics list, upon completing the data analysis. Currently, our focus is on securing further data-taking beam time. The findings from Phase- α will provide valuable insights as we progress towards the muon-to-electron conversion process search in Phase-I.

References

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